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Foreign Policy of Equal and Near Equals: Insights in Kenya's Relation with Brazil

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Abstract

A number of dispositional factors describe states in international environment; colonized and uncolonized states, small states and big states, economic giants and weak economies, the South – North divide, developing against developed, and superpower versus other states. Whereas some of the descriptions overlap and others lack clear description of state groupings, from the global alignment of states exists equal and near equal states an observation that we enhance as a new concept. This generally sets an unofficial trend of state security in international dealings. In this article, the authors find it necessary to discuss the insights of foreign policy behavior of equal and near equal states with Kenya and Brazil in mind, wherein we argue that there is an affinity developed in such relations. Secondly and finally, we focus on specific socio-eco-political impacts of cooperation between Kenya and Brazil. Within these parameters we interrogated the operations of foreign policy within the conceptual limits in our topic. We concluded that there are merits in relating with equal and near equals but no state should use this framework to close its doors to other global players hence the reason why Kenya and Brazil continue to take the bilateral and multilateral policy directions that they advance within international hemisphere. Suffice to say they cannot move in a single-loop directional foreign policy trajectory but to embrace a multi-loop directional approach. It is of great merit in foreign policy when equal and near equal states promotes bilateral relations, multilateralism, and joint co-operations which Kenya and Brazil have exercised through opening and maintaining fully-fledged missions, an exchange that Vienna Convention on state relations uphold

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1.0 The Foreign Policy Behavior of Equal and Near Equal States

Foreign policy (As, 2018) definitively attracts various views from scholars; however, they are certain that it is concerned with behavior of a state towards other states. Herman defined foreign policy as “the discrete purposeful action that results from the political level decision of an individual or group of individuals. It is the observable artifact of a political level decision. It is not the decision but a product of the decision.” Reflectively, Herman defines foreign policy as the behavior of states. According to Laura (2008), George Modelski on the

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other hand defines it as “the system of activities evolved by communities for changing the behavior of other states and for adjusting their own activities to the international environment.

In Hume Gibson’s insight (1944), “foreign policy is a well-rounded comprehensive plan based on knowledge and experience for conducting the business of government with the rest of the world. It’s aimed at promoting and protecting the interests of the nations. This calls for a clear understanding of what those interests are and how far we hope to go with the means at our disposal. Anything less than this, falls short of being a foreign policy”.

1.1 Conceptualizing “*Equal and Near Equal States*” in Foreign Policy

The concept of equal and near equal states in our view by and large revolves around states as either superpowers (militarily/economically powerful) or weak states within the international system which is the natural order of states existence. In this context it is construed that there is a way equal and near equal states behave as far as foreign policy is concerned. Illustratively, this concept of equal or near equal states can follow in our considered view *shadow-sun analogy* to emphasize its flexibility. It behoves this authorship to relook at meanings of foreign policy to clarify understanding.

In our observation, at the heart of foreign policy in a complex systemic global arena is decision-making which is an activity to be pursued by representation. How it is undertaken is capable to alteration and most often alters the state’s (or other state’s) image in the community of states as it attracts response and counter-response behavior economically and socio-politically. Understanding foreign policy requires being abreast with its ecological framework which is the international system.

International system analysis seems to emphasize on a clear academic criteria to understand the highly complex problems in world politics. This system analysis in political science apply three widely accepted generalization (or abstraction), *being the individual, state (or, society), and the international system*. As Weber (2021) suggests, moral principles of *individuals* may translate into that of nations then into international, the power of *state* translates into the national interest of that state hence as power-seeking entities they enter into competition with other state actors, and the relations between states are necessarily anarchic being the logic of *the international system* compelling states to act as self-preserving and power-seeking entities in a global scope.

The notions expressed align with the Idealism, Realism, and Neorealism thoughts of Kant and Wilson, Hobbes and Morgenthau, and Rousseau and Waltz respectively. In addition to the argument, there is need to project level of analysis from Marxism perspective of class since societies (nations) exist as antagonistic organisms defined by those who own the means of production, the bourgeois class (such as factories, capital, and technological prowess) and those who do not, the proletarian class thus creating competition and conflict naturally.

Distinct foreign policy behavior of equal or near equal states exist in form of *great powers* for example results into (Chhabra, Doshi, Hass, and Kimball, 2020) a major role on questions regarding geopolitical stability, global and national economic growth, emerging technology, and international values and institutions. At the same time, the fast-deteriorating relationship between two countries such as USA and China will also form the broad structure within which the other great powers maneuver. Key development in great power politics is the strong position taken often such as that of Washington and Beijing relative to the other great powers. Indeed, with both countries’ economic and military strength and leadership in technologies like artificial intelligence, the United States and China are outpacing the other great powers — and that gap is growing. In light of this widening separation, it is increasingly clear that decisions made in Beijing and Washington will play such key roles globally.

These roles display foreign policy reaction and response in two ways; as a collaborative partner through an alliance to one side or being an uncollaborative partner (a foe) in the power balancing just as it was in the cold war. The foreign policy here then will involve behavior through activities reflective of the side. Already this is visible as further highlighted by (Chhabra, Doshi, Hass, and Kimball, 2020), when for China, stabilizing

ties with other great powers provides a hedge against the downturn in relations with the United States. China's neighboring great power, Russia, has also seen its ties with China improve whereas as this occurs, Trans-Atlantic coordination is critical to the success of any U.S. China strategy, particularly because Europe's economic size, technology base, and liberal values give it influence in the very domains increasingly at the center of the U.S.-China rivalry.

A glance from Lebanon reveals a syndrome that can affect foreign policy of equal or near equals among developing countries. Felsch (2017) asserts foreign policy analysis often gives exclusive attention to great powers or 'strong states'. Weak states are usually ignored as international actors due to their 'systemic ineffectiveness'. For a better understanding of the foreign policy of weak states and a look at Lebanon as a case in point, it's weakness does not only stem from military, economic or size factors, but also from the divisions of its multi-confessional society and its consociational political system. As a consequence, Lebanon is unable to agree on a national foreign policy agenda and, instead, produces multiple and inconsistent foreign policies. Lebanon's domestic identity groups enjoy a relatively high level of political autonomy and pursue their domestic interests in the international arena. Thus, domestic and foreign policy overlap tremendously. Many near equals from developing states have inconsistencies that render them weak on their own.

1.2 Picturesque of Kenya – Brazil Foreign Policy

Kenya and Brazil exceptionally have foreign policies which have been carefully crafted to project their behaviour in the international system. Kenya's foreign policy is specific and general but guided by the constitution and the foreign policy document. As is stated in Republic of Kenya ROK (2014),

“the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and International Trade is mandated to pursue Kenya's foreign policy and international trade affairs in accordance to the Constitution of Kenya, with the overarching objective of protecting, promoting and projecting the nation's interests abroad. The Policy is inclined towards upholding the country's sovereignty, promoting universal peace and fostering better relations with our neighbors, the rest of the African continent and the world at large. Kenya will continue to consolidate and strengthen its foreign relations and diplomatic engagements with other countries as well as international and multilateral organizations at the regional, continental and international level. This Policy is anchored on five interlinked pillars of diplomacy namely: Economic; Peace; Environmental; Cultural and Diaspora.”

In recent years Brazil has pursued a more ambitious foreign policy that aims to expand the country's presence in global economic negotiations, multilateral institutions and regional affairs (Hirst, De Lima, & Regina, 2006; Hurrell, 2008). According to Hirst (2009) the concept of foreign policy equal and near equal states is echoed. She opines that Brazil's role in international relations has altered somewhat in recent years. Under President Luiz 'Lula' da Silva, presidential diplomacy has dominated an active foreign policy. His has involved deepening ties with both industrialized economies and the emergent South. Such a multi-polar approach is evident in Brazil's renewed relations with the United States (US) and Europe - arguably on a more equal footing than in the past - along with closer ties to China, India, Russia and South Africa. On this note it is imperative to interrogate the how-about of Kenya-Brazil relations through the lens of the same concept.

Relevant to Kenya from Brazil could be strategic partnership where Kenya would consider herself as near equal state and cooperation in improvement of agriculture given the strain and struggles Kenya continues to experience in her food security. Importantly, this draws from Hirst (2009) summary evaluation of Brazil foreign policy within her region which she sums by suggesting that Brazil, regional affairs - and particularly regional affairs in South America - have assumed unprecedented importance. Ties with Argentina deepened even more as former rivalries were replaced by a 'strategic partnership', combining asymmetric interdependency, political co-ordination and permanent security co-operation. It has also been a very successful exporter of agricultural goods, which has informed its position on global trade negotiations. Again, the expansion of Brazil's regional co-operative security agenda has evolved in tandem with its increased involvement in peacekeeping activities.

Brazil's relations (Abdenur and de Souza Neto 2014) with Africa have focused mainly on the economic and political dimensions, but Brazilian stakeholders have also paid increasing attention to African security issues. Both foreign policy, which has sought to deepen ties with Africa, and Brazil's new national defense strategy, with its renewed focus on the South Atlantic, have made Africa one of the country's top priorities abroad. Brazil's engagement with security in Africa is marked by a tension inherent in its status as a rising power: Brazilian policy elites' desire to transform the country into a global player and their insistence on respect for national sovereignty. She seeks to become more of a norms setter in international relations, for which a role in African security has become essential. In January 2014 the importance of African security to Brazilian foreign policy was underscored by Brazil's election as chair of the United Nations (UN) Peace building Commission. However, Brazil's involvement with African security issues is still piecemeal and occurring primarily through indirect channels.

Closer ties with Kenya are demonstrated in the report of the Embassy of the Republic of Kenya in Brasilia that Brazil considers Kenya an important partner in the East African region. It established a resident diplomatic mission in Nairobi in 1967. Kenya opened its Embassy in Brasilia in October 2006. Former President Luiz Inácio Lula da Silva made his first official visit to Kenya from 5th – 6th July, 2010. This was the first visit by a Brazilian President to Kenya. Among key activities cementing the ties include; the Kenya/Brazil Joint Commission for Cooperation (JCC) of 2005, Kenya's Ambassador to Brazil led a team of industrialists and business executives from Brazil for bilateral talks with the President and various government officials, Agreements signed by Kenya and Brazil in various sectors such as agriculture (for training opportunities in the areas of food security, rural development and capacity building for small scale farming), \$80 million credit to Kenya to support financing of farming equipment and infrastructure, and Kenya purchased the first batch of 2000 doses of bull semen from Brazil in October 2016 (www.kenyaembassybrazil.com.br/kenya-brazil-relations).

Historically, the impacts of Brazil's foreign policy did not evolve over night. It was a product of *the mission in the objectives, a gradual redefinition, and embrace of transformational path* as her national interest. Marcos Aurelio Guedes de Oliveira in 2017 observed transformational impact of Brazil's national interest as the most important issues of Brazilian Foreign policy were set at the Monarchical years and in the first decades of the Republic. They were: (i) to clearly establish Brazil's territorial borders; (ii) to overcome dependence, to achieve economic development and to become a global trader; (iii) to be a global player on issues of regional and international affairs. The Brazilian Foreign Office, known as Itamaraty, served well the Monarchy and adapted itself to serve even better the Republic. It gradually developed a sense of how Brazil should find its own way in the Eurocentric world order. Not much different to the Military concern on order and progress, the idea of modernization was taken by the national diplomacy as the centre piece of Brazil's national interest.

Kenya relating with Brazil as with other countries requires Brazil to understand the geopolitical infrastructure as Mabera (2016) asserts, Kenya's foreign policy orientation has situated it as a benign regional leader, but pressing developments in the regional and international environments have edged it towards a more assertive foreign policy position. It is the economic powerhouse of East Africa and a long-standing hub for multilateral diplomacy.

Amidst enhancement of foreign policy of equal and near equal, United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA) observes that South to South migration accounted for 34 % of global migration in 2012 while the United Nations noted an increase of South to South migration by 57 % during the period from 2007-2015 (Bogonko, 2019). The historical diaspora were established due to involuntary migration to the areas of Brazil, the Caribbean and sections of North America and Europe whereas the contemporary diaspora has for the most part arisen from voluntary migration (Republic of Kenya, 2014). What this would mean to foreign policy actors is to assuage such issues arising from such relations to ensure an open door to tap ensuing benefits.

The focus of foreign policy (Obala, 2013) in any respect does not appear to be new. Writing about Kenya, Obala points that it is largely made of patches from the past regimes and the Jubilee Coalition seems to ably represent the country. Kenya's foreign policy to reflect *an assertive new Africa-centered approach* as the

central plank of Nairobi's regional and global policy to the traditional "look West" policy, or the emerging "look east policy". However, despite the rhetoric against western countries within the same manifesto, the coalition asserts that it will engage the traditional economic powers, including the United States, the United Kingdom and other European countries, and emerging players such as China, Brazil, India and Russia. The Foreign Policy Pillars captured from Uhuru Kenyatta's April 2013 inauguration speech implied the basis of his emphasis when he mentioned *regional security, free movement of goods and people, reliance, the strengthening of regional bodies* and, most importantly, *the equality of nations*. It would appear that Kenya's overall foreign policy has no clear direction but with proper stipulations as of now, there is *an enduring nature of foreign policy* to states that is never erased by advocacy type of transformations by new entrants in executives.

Despite uniqueness of foreign policy orientations as aptly discussed pitying '*strong/big near equals* against *small/weak near equals*', Baskin (2011) opines a prevalent framework of world politics plays decisive role in deciding the foreign policy of a country. As such foreign policies of states thus change with shifts in the international power structure. In the traditional multi-polar system, it was easier for states to switch sides and gain maximum interests from both sides. Italy has used switching sides as a strategy skillfully during the height of World War I (WWI) to gain its share in the post war colonial arrangement.

Additionally, since foreign policy is acted through diplomacy, Juma, Kurgat, and Gitonga, 2020 argue then that bearing in mind the complexity of the contemporary international environment, transformations in the structures of diplomacy indicate the ways in which the state is responding to and managing change. In a more analytical sense, whether at the behest of 'big or small states', diplomacy of 21st century has no uniformity of conceived thought among international relation scholars. They concur changes exist but it projects continuity of same practice in different environmental dispensations. There is a marked visibility and invisibility of 'big and small states' alike in the 21st century diplomacy. Whereas the crossroads exist in diplomacy, it is not new in the field of international relations where previously it existed in terms of polar divide of USA and allies against USSR and allies. The crossroads has shifted again clearly depicting USA – Western Eurocentric viz a vis Sinocentric divide. The 'small states' diplomacy in the twenty first century finds itself torn in between both for political and economic ends.

2.0 Socio-Eco-Political Impacts of Cooperation between Kenya and Brazil

The cooperation between Kenya and Brazil sets back after shortly after Kenya's independence in 1963. The diplomatic relations between the two countries say the opening up of residence embassies both in Nairobi and Brazil in 1967 and 2005 respectively. The urge for Brazil-African cooperation has increased its diplomatic presence in Africa, through embassies in more than 37 offices in Africa. The continent has benefited in several multilateral initiatives developed by Brazil to promote its cooperation with African countries. Moreover, there is a considerable increase in the trade between Brazil and Africa with large Brazilian companies investing in the continent. Kenya has benefited socially, economically, and politically through its cooperation with Brazil. It is important to point out that the diplomatic presence of Brazil in Kenya has contributed immensely to the development and growth of different sectors ranging from agricultural, trade, education, energy, social protection among others. The number of visits by the heads of the state indicates the new Brazil commitments to Africa. Moreover, large business delegations accompanied by foreign and economic ministers have solidified relations and Brazilian presence in Africa. Rural Development, the Fight for Hunger, and Dialogue on Food Security are some of the thematic events. Brazil has contributed to African development through assistance and technical expertise transfer.

The promotion of the South-South development cooperation cause has quickly become the Brazilian core activity in advancing its foreign policy agenda. In (2006-2010), the Brazilian government under Lula's regime championed for development cooperation as one of its strategic instrument for championing cooperation in Africa (Alves, 2014). Brazil uses various modalities in development cooperation such as contributing to international organizations, technical cooperation, scholarships for foreigners, and humanitarian assistance. The Brazilian Cooperation Agency and the Institute for Economic Applied Research (IPEA) in their 2010 study

indicated that Brazil had invested \$ 1.7 billion between 2005 and 2009 for development resources. 76 percent of these resources went to peacekeeping operations, regional banks, and contributions to international organizations. Africa received a lion share of from the nine percent set aside for technical cooperation. 10 percent of the resources went to scholarships for foreign students and five percent to humanitarian aid.

Deeper ties between Africa and Brazil continue to be exhibited in the 21st century, hence a likelihood for further solidification. The currents of Africa's economic growth indicate convergence with Brazil's political stability and economic development. African countries seem to attract more trade and investment relations as the negative inheritance of the colonial days' fades away (Vinicius de Freitas, 2016). Sub-Saharan African countries benefit from Brazil relations in five key areas which include; social protection, energy, vocational training, tropical agriculture, and tropical medicine. Between 2000 to 2010, the trade between Brazil and Sub-Saharan Africa had increased from the US \$ 2 billion to the US \$ 12 billion respectively (Vinicius de Freitas, 2016).

Kenya has benefited from the growing number of Brazilian companies opening their doors locally and within the continent. Exports and imports from Brazil have increased due to the ever-increasing of the bilateral and intra-industry trade between the two countries (Vinicius de Freitas, 2016). There is an increased interaction between Brazil and Kenya due to the number of steps that have been used by both countries to secure the ever-growing partnerships of equals in multilateral action, trade, and business. In 2010, Kenya and Brazil signed a trade deal consisting of six key agreements that focused on enhancing the economic, investment, and trade ties. The deal was signed in Nairobi by the third President of Kenya and his Counterpart President Luiz Inacio Lula of Brazil. Other agreements were on investment and trade promotion, education, and on the performance of remunerated services activities by dependents of administrative, technical, military, consular, and diplomatic staff. The open sky agreement has enabled direct flights from Kenya to Brazil hence stronger relationships among the two countries. The prices of the tickets have become more competitive and the air services have improved significantly.

Several cultural and political forums have been initiated by Brazil to deepen the ties with Africa through multi-thematic events such as the Brazil-Africa Forum. Government officials and civil societies and academicians are brought together through high ranking biennial summits. Thematic events such as, have been used to exchange knowledge and intensify contacts. Social protection, vocational training agriculture, and health and culture are the four major areas that Brazil has focused on its knowledge exchange with Sub-Saharan countries (Seibert, 2019). In the past decades, these areas have seen a significant accumulation of expertise and expansion. In the long run, they have formed the core of Brazil's technical cooperation in international development. During Presidents Lula da Silva's tenure (2003-10), these areas received an unprecedented scale-up.

Biofuel forms part of the Brazil-Africa agenda, this is an area that demonstrates strong potential for the Africa cooperation based on the major technological strides made by Brazil. Africa faces significant challenges in the energy sector hence presenting a gap that can be tapped for international development. Brazilian expertise in areas of development and management of the insurance markets, capacity building in the public service, strategic planning, leadership, and management continue to receive high demand from African countries.

Kenya has benefited from the exchange of best practices on budget planning from the Brazilian experts. It has also received technical assistance on environmental protection, soccer coaches have received training from their Brazilian counterparts. Brazilian experts have contributed knowledge to the Kenyan medics on the fight against HIV/AIDS. Moreover, the development of handicraft production forms part of the expertise gains that Kenya has so far received from Brazil.

Several factors such as biodiversity, tropical location, climatic and geological advantages, and the size of the territory have contributed significantly to Brazil's success in tropical agricultural production. Moreover, the promotion of domestic production, microeconomic, and political stability of the country has promoted agricultural growth. Brazil implemented structural reforms such as the elimination of non-tariff, privatization of state-owned, policy changes, the establishment of Mercosur customs are some of the factors that have

contributed to the trivial of agriculture in Brazil (OECD, 2005). Brazil was able to achieve the Millennium goals for poverty and hunger much earlier before the schedule, one of the contributing factors was related to President Lula da Silva's agricultural policies. The National System for Food and Nutritional Security is one of the policies that was used by the Lula da Silva regime to improve agricultural development and food security of Brazil (IPEA, 2010).

There was a reduction of poverty and inequality and increased social inclusion due to the innovative policy reforms that led to the improvement of agricultural production. However, for the case of the sub-Saharan countries, most of them import energy and food. The lack of qualified labor, poor infrastructure, and low productivity characterizes the agricultural sector of these countries (ADB, 2011).

Kenya makes an ideal country for agricultural cooperation with Brazil amidst the other Sub-Saharan countries. These countries share similar climatic and geological characteristics that make them ideal for joint projects are research. Therefore, Kenya has benefited immensely from the agricultural exchange programs, research, and extension projects based on the success of Brazil in these areas. The Ministry of Agrarian Development and EMBRAPA is the key governmental institutions that contributed to the success of agricultural development and food security in Brazil. Through EMBRAPA, an institution formed in 1973, Brazil was able to reduce its dependence on external inputs, conserved natural resources, increased food production, and reduced production costs. It also played a significant role in the development and recommendation of over 9000 technologies that could be used in agricultural production in Brazil.

Brazil has strengthened its relations in Africa through EMBRAPA, as one of the world's best tropical agricultural institution. The institution has invested much of its efforts in bioenergy and biotechnology, it has also received recognition for its efforts towards the transformation of the Brazilian savannah through technological innovations. EMBRAPA opened its offices in Africa in 2006 in Accra, Ghana, and continues to increase its presence in Sub-Saharan Africa.

Kenya among the other Sub-Saharan countries has benefited from Brazil's cooperation through EMBRAPA programs. For instance, EMBRAPA has advanced its support to African countries through the Africa-Brazil Platform for Agricultural Innovation, technical training, and structuring projects (Simon and Jeremy, 2010). This organization has played an important role in agricultural research through multilateral agreements and technical cooperation. Agricultural development has been advanced through the placement of researchers in agricultural centers and the provision of virtual laboratories through LABEX. Through EMBRAPA, Brazil can maintain projects in international cooperation through technological advancement, the share of knowledge, and scientific activities among the partner countries.

Brazil supports African countries through structuring projects as one of its unique approach to bilateral cooperation. These types of projects are customized based on the economic conditions and the local biome. A participative approach is employed through out and long term experimental farms to vocational training among other capacity building developments are used to ensure long term cooperation (Simon and Jeremy, 2009). Through CECAT, EMBRAPA provides technical training to countries benefitting from its support. Technical training forms an important instrument in advancing the objectives. A significant number of researchers and technicians have participated in the training programs by CECAT. Through this project, African peers take part in Brazilian agriculture, soy production, water resources conservation, community seed production, family-based agricultural production systems, livestock production, seed production, pasture and forage production, and best practices in agricultural management (Simon and Jeremy, 2010).

The Agricultural Innovation Marketplace is the third instrument used by EMBRAPA in advancing ties with African researchers. Kenyan researchers benefited from the training on sweet sorghum varietal adaptation for ethanol production. Participants in these projects could seek funding of up to the US \$ 80,000 for their projects. Through this program, Brazilian and Kenyan researchers promoted agricultural innovations and south-south collaborations. The World Bank, the United Kingdom Fund for Agricultural Development, International Fund for Agricultural Development, Forum for Agricultural Research in Africa, and the ABC are among the participants' key participants in the marketplace.

Brazil has advanced its interests in boosting cotton production in Kenya. Burundi and Tanzania are also included in this economic cooperation. The three East African countries signed an agreement with Brazil on the Cotton Victoria project in October 2016. The initiative focused on strengthening the cotton sector in the Lake Victoria basin at a cost of \$ 13 million a four years' project. Brazil and Kenya made an export deal due to the growing demand for Brazil's poultry genetic materials. The deal was approved after negotiations between the Veterinary Service of Kenya and the Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock, and Food Supply (MAPA) of Brazil.

The advanced research to the fight against Malaria, sickle-cell, the development of national milk-bank networks, and immunization campaigns are among health programs that Brazil has done successfully. Moreover, the fight against the spread of HIV/AIDS through the distribution of free anti-viral drugs proved to work effectively in Brazil. This is some of the critical areas towards the fight against diseases that Kenya has benefited from success stories from Brazil. The Brazilian bilateral agreements with African countries had a component of HIV/AIDS and malaria projects. Before 2008, Brazilian cooperation relied on small-scale health projects before its restructuring to development structuring orientation (Mateos, 2011). These projects aimed at strengthening local and national institutions and enabling human resources. Capacity development, local engagement, and long-term approach were at the center of these types of projects.

In relation to Africa, Brazil has strong economic interests in the African Continent. Africa in the 2000s coincided with the globalization of the Brazilian economy based on the stability and dynamics of the continent. Africa presents endless opportunities for Brazilian investors based on its social, economic, climatic, and geological similarities with Brazil. The Brazil-Africa investment and trade flows over the past decades reflect the Brazilian technology and expertise in telecommunications, mining, exploration, hydrocarbons, infrastructure construction, biofuels, agribusiness, and tropical agriculture.

Brazil successfully declared oil self-sufficiency in 2006 after reducing oil consumption due to its investments in biofuel and oil production. Large oil reserves were discovered hence a game-changer in the revision of the international energy strategy that enabled it to venture into exportation (Petrobras, 2009). Brazil deepened its exploration in alternative sources of energy based on the rapid growth of global energy exploration, environmental and social concerns, geopolitical risks of oil dependence, and limited availability of fossil sources. Biofuels promise new markets for farmers and provide major relevance based on less environmental damages (MME, 2011). The United States and Brazil are among the leading producers of biofuel in the world. For instance, Brazil accounts for 42% and the United States 46% of the world's biofuel production share (EIA, 2009).

From her agriculture, Brazil relies on the production of biodiesel and ethanol through the use of soybeans and sugarcane respectively. Based on FAO (2009) report, Brazil became the world's largest producer of sugarcane based on targeted public policies and favorable climatic and geological conditions. Technological advancements in agriculture that have enhanced the use of genetically modified plants that has enabled the production of sugarcane as initially, the plants could do well due to the unsuitable and fragile soils in the country. The Centro Tecnológico de Piracicaba and EMBRAPA played a critical role in advancing biofuel production and cultivation.

Sub-Saharan Africa could benefit from Brazil's experience from public policies and technological advancements that strengthened family-based agriculture in energy production. Local farmers could benefit from sugarcane production based on its unique characteristic such as not easy to export in comparison to soybeans hence local processing was highly recommended. The Brazilian model of agricultural production has so far made sense in African countries that depend on imports for energy and food. Kenya has so far benefited from joint projects and private in areas of energy such as ethanol production.

Large power systems, power sector reforms, and power crisis management are the areas that Brazil could share its experiences with the African countries. Petrobras, a Brazilian State-owned oil company is among the leading oil companies in the world has its activities in many African countries such as Tanzania, Nigeria, Gabon, Benin, Nigeria, Senegal among others (Petrobras, 2011). The company has invested heavily in biodiesel

production as one of its strategies in ensuring global leadership. Sub-Saharan countries could benefit from these experiences in biofuels production through cooperation.

Charcoal production is another area that Sub-Saharan African countries have benefited from producing this type of fuel sustainably and efficiently. For instance, Brazil has been able to reduce the dependence of natural forests for charcoal through public universities and private companies' efforts in ensuring the quality production of dedicated fuelwood plantations. Kenya could have greatly benefited from the enhanced capacity in charcoal production. Higher charcoal productivity, deforestation, and co-generated electricity are some of the areas that Sub-Saharan Africa could benefit from in strategic development. African Charcoal production has contributed significantly to deforestation through its inefficient, unsustainable, and traditional methods of charcoal production.

Brazil launched several projects to enhance social protection, due to the large number of inequality that this Latin American country faced. The Zero Hunger program was among the successful programs that Brazil carried out amid its fight against hunger. However, several policies have been enacted to fight marginalization and hunger. Bolsa Familia is one of the best programs that was used by Brazil to fight hunger under the Zero Hunger program. Several existing social programs were done under an institutional umbrella through a conditional cash transfer program. Income generation, adult literacy is some of the complementary social projects that were used to boost families' progress and development. Families were also helped to overcome the intergenerational cycle of poverty through direct cash transfers to provide immediate relief (MDS, 2009).

Bolsa Familia is an inter-sectoral program that covers different areas such as the prevention and recovery of children from child labor, education, and health. There is shared management through decentralization of across various levels of government and across agencies. The monitoring of the projects is done by the different municipal and state government ministries in areas of education, health, and social assistance. This successful implementation of the social programs in Brazil has resulted in their replication in other developing countries. For instance, more than 60 countries have benefited from these projects including Kenya, Senegal, and Angola. For instance, in 2009 the government of Angola turned to projects that aimed at reducing regional disparities, fighting poverty and hunger, promoting and protecting the rights of the vulnerable groups. Enhancement of quality agricultural products, food, and nutrition security, hydropower resources, biodiesel are some of the joint projects that were initiated in Senegal in 2005, and in 2011, the program was launched in Kenya.

Higher education and sports are other critical areas that have a significant impact on the cooperation between Kenya and Brazil. For instance, Brazil has focused on the promotion of primary education in Portuguese-speaking countries run and traditionally organized by civil society. For sustainable development and human capacity, in the mid-2000s Brazil turned its focus on strengthening higher education in Africa. African countries were attracted to some programs and replicated them based on Brazil's experience such as the Paulo Freire's methods and innovative pedagogical tools and the use of IT. Sub-Saharan Africa would benefit immensely from vocational training and higher education (ACBF, 2011).

In 2010, Brazil officially launched the Federal University for Luso-Afro-Brazilian Integration. The main of this university was to enhance cultural links Brazil and Lusophone countries in Africa and the rest of the while providing higher education opportunities to both the students and teachers. The Open University of Mozambique was also formed through the support from the Brazilian government and four of Mozambique's institutions in public administration, pedagogy, biology, and mathematics. The corporation led to the joint provision of academic disciplines through onsite and virtual learning with dual certification from both Brazil and Mozambique universities.

Brazil's government has created scholarship opportunities for both undergraduate and postgraduate students from Kenya to study in Brazil. However, the program faces challenges such as inadequate funding for the undergraduate levels and the incompatible levels of education. Brazil has strengthened direct dialogue with Sub-Saharan Africa universities. A good example is the Federal de Vicosa that presents an intensive

engagement. The university developed an institutionalized approach from the professors and researchers from both Brazil and Africa.

A significant number of African students have benefited from scholarships from the Brazilian government both nationally and internationally. The Unilab, an African University was inaugurated by Brazil to strengthen its future relations with African Countries. Through the exchange Program for Undergraduate Students (PEC-G), young Kenyans have benefited from educational wise through this program. Students have the opportunity to advance their undergraduate studies in Brazilian Higher Education. The exchange program was first initiated in 1965 by Brazil to offer educational, cultural, or scientific and technological advancement opportunities for students from developing countries (Seibert, 2011).

Stiff competition from China forms one of the challenges that exist between Kenya and Brazil relations. However, the prospects of Brazil Kenya's relations seem very promising as in the past decades, Brazil-Kenya trade and investment flows have made remarkable progress. Kenya faces specific challenges such as scarcity of qualified labor, inefficient institutional framework (the heavy bureaucracy), unstable regulatory framework, and unattractive investment environment and infrastructural bottlenecks. However, on the Brazilian side, some of its companies at times have poor corporate social responsibility practices, inadequate financial support, poor efficiency in diplomatic, institutional, and logistical support.

Vinicius de Freitas (2016) predicts future challenges in its relations with the African countries. For instance, Brazil on several occasions has faced an unstable political environment. However, the cries come and with time fade away. For instance, historically, the country on several occasions has been able to overcome its challenges and make strides in growth and development. However, its ties with Africa are stronger. Different political uncertainties on both sides of the Atlantic have in several ways threatened the partnership intensities that have some time been of higher and lower intensities.

However, positive results have been achieved through the South-South relationship as Brazil has tapped cooperation and economic growth. The country's investment policy could be affected based on the numerous corruption scandals that Brazil has faced involving its largest company, Petrobras (Vinicius de Freitas, 2016). Brazil has on several occasions has been criticized for how it manages and coordinates the SSDC that could cripple its support to countries that benefit from its support. For instance, Cabral and Weinstock (2010) argued that the design of the Brazilian regulatory framework largely focused on receiving rather than providing assistance. The decision making of the *Itamaraty gets* weakened as the institution involved in providing assistance continues to expand (Cabral and Weinstock, 2010).

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